

TEACHING VOCABULARY TO PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to helping readers to make vocabulary teaching more effective for primary class students and some useful strategies in teaching vocabulary. This article also describes the main problems encountered in learning vocabulary among primary classes. Moreover, it provides further data on effective ways of learning new words and some mistakes made in teaching.

Keywords: teaching, strategies, vocabulary, primary classes, effective ways.

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Vocabulary is the most essential component of any language. Without enough sources of lexis, learners are not able to express opinions. Primary class pupils sometimes find challenging to learn by heart new words and they forget easily what they have learnt during the class. A number of methodologists and teachers suggest several solutions to overcome this problem and it is also a key to developing reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills. According to Thornbury's opinion without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. It means if someone is good at grammar but lacks vocabulary, it will be useless if they do not know the vocabulary. In addition, Ur states that vocabulary is one of the most important things to be taught in learning a foreign language because it will be impossible to speak up without a variety of words.

The Uzbek and English languages are different from each other and both of them have different pronunciations and spelling. In the English language, the pronounced word is quite different from the spelling. Learners face some difficulties while they are learning vocabulary, especially in primary classes. English is not the mother tongue for young learners and so it is difficult for them. Thus, the teacher is required to make some interesting ways to teach the words. Besides, not all learners are not the same and not all of them learn new words very quickly. So, the teacher needs to think "How can pupils learn new words effectively?". In order to solve this problem, the teacher always checks the learners' abilities and interests.

In primary classes, students learn the basic vocabulary items, the names of the objects which include people, parts of the body, animals, fruits, classroom objects,

personal pronouns, and the most essential verbs in order to make easy sentences, but most of the words belong to nouns.

In Uzbekistan, primary classes include ages from 7 to 11 years. First-grade pupils cannot write and they are able to learn through interesting games. Although, they are young and eager to learn, they face several problems during the learning process. Firstly, students learn the vocabulary during the class after the lessons never repeat these words and they never use this learnt vocabulary in the context. Secondly, parents are so busy with their work that they do not have time to learn with the learners, consequently, young learners are demotivated. Moreover, the English language is totally new for the learners and they face some difficulties in pronouncing the words some teachers do not pay attention to their pronunciation. Young learners learn by heart the words with the wrong accent. In addition, some pupils go to kindergarten and they learn common words here. They get bored during the class to learn the same words over again whereas these words are completely new for other participants. Furthermore, there are some reasons for the lesson is to become boring. When learners are sleepy, hungry, or tired they cannot draw their attention to the class.

There are some effective ways to solve the issues and make the lessons more interesting. Primary class students are young to learn the words sitting on the table and learn with a dictionary. There are some techniques of teaching vocabulary suggested by some experts and methodologists:

1. Using objects to teach vocabulary.

This strategy is highly useful for young learners because memory for objects and pictures is relatively reliable, and visual strategies can act as prompts for recalling words. This strategy makes the use of visual aids and demonstrations.

Furthermore, the real objects technique is appropriate for beginners or young learners, while presenting realistic vocabulary. When the vocabulary consists of concrete nouns, objects might be utilized to demonstrate meaning. Introducing a new word by displaying a real-world object frequently aids learners in memorizing the word through visualization. Objects in the classroom or items brought in from outside the school can be used.

2. Using drills, spelling, and active participation to teach vocabulary.

Drilling is used to help students get familiar with word forms, particularly how they sound. Drilling is essential for young children to accurately enunciate the term, as previously noted. Drilling should be straightforward and natural in order to familiarize learners with the term. Drilling is essential because students must repeat the phrases to themselves as they learn them in order to retain them from memory. Memorizing words is the fundamental method of spelling. Because spelling forms of English words are not usually deduced from pronunciation, word

spelling must be taken into account. The instructor uses this strategy to urge pupils to elicit the meaning of a term. Elicitation increases the amount of time that students speak. Using this strategy, the teacher encourages pupils to elicit the meaning of the term. Elicitation increases learners' speaking possibilities and serves as a means of assessing learners' comprehension. This strategy also incorporates personalizing, which is when learners use the term in a context or sentence that is relevant to their lives. In relation to the aforementioned strategies, instructors are advised to perform as many planned presentations of vocabulary as feasible, hence it is preferable that teachers communicate word meaning by combining more than one strategy.

3. Teaching vocabulary with using different mimes, expressions, and gestures.

The term "mime or gesture" is useful since it stresses the significance of gestures and facial expressions in communication. In essence, it can be used not just to illustrate the meaning of a word discovered in a reading passage, but also in speaking activities because it emphasizes communication. Mime, expressions, and gestures can be used to introduce several words. Teachers use a lot of gestures, especially when speaking to young students or beginners. For primary classes pantomimes are useful for them especially in teaching adjectives. For instance, to show feelings such as "happy" or "sad". They may use their facial expression. Teaching gestures may be useful for learners' memorization in addition to supporting comprehension. Indeed, many second language teachers who employ gestures as a teaching approach claim that they aid students in memorizing the second language lexicon. Many of them have found that when the teacher makes the gesture linked with the lexical item throughout the class, students may quickly retrieve the word. Others have observed students, particularly young learners, voluntarily repeating the motion when uttering the word. Many people have seen the effect of gestures on memorization, but it has rarely been studied in a systematic and empirical manner.

4. Using interactive games.

The best way to learn new words is to play with them. The games are a useful tool for learning vocabulary as they promote interaction and stick in a children's memory. According to Lewis (1999), games are popular among children because they enjoy playing. Young learners could interact, discover, and experiment with their surroundings through games. The usage of games not only increases students' interest, but also serves as an incentive and stimulus to utilize the language. Using games to teach vocabulary to young learners necessitates qualified teachers who engage children in play while also mastering the linguistic aspect of the language. According to Rixon (1981), knowing games will assist teachers in finding and developing games that would allow their pupils to learn while having fun.

To sum up, taking into consideration all abilities of primary class students, they can learn the language through the games, songs, and interesting activities, games, and also motivation plays a crucial role in their learning process. Teachers carefully choose vocabulary they want to teach and the words are taught in a fun and active way so that learners can learn easily and interesting way.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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